

Determination of heavy metals in vital organs (liver, kidney, and gills) of two fish species from the Head Balloki on River Ravi, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

The current study was aimed at a comparative analysis of heavy metals (lead, cadmium, and chromium) concentrations in the gills, kidneys, and liver of two fish species (*Catla catla* and *Labeo rohita* from Head Balloki, Pattoki, Punjab, Pakistan). The atomically coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer was used to assess heavy metal concentrations in selected tissues. Three major heavy metals—chromium, cadmium, and lead were examined in tissues. Heavy metal concentrations varied significantly depending on the type of fish tissue. Lead exhibits higher concentrations than chromium and cadmium in the kidney, liver, and gills. In case of liver the concentration of lead in *L. rohita* was 0.033 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) and in *C. catla* was 0.044 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), in case of gills the concentration of lead in *L. rohita* was 0.011 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) and in *C. catla* was 0.025 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) while in case of kidney the concentration of lead in *L. rohita* was 0.16 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) and in *C. catla* was 0.214 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg). The order of concentration of lead in the tissues of both fish was kidney>liver>gills. Elevated levels of lead found in the organs of fish suggest that the fish may be at risk of harm. Among the studied metals, the order of concentration of heavy metals was lead >chromium>cadmium. The order of concentration of cadmium, chromium, and lead in *L. rohita* and *C. catla* tissue was kidney>gills>liver. Also, *L. rohita* was found to have a higher heavy metal accumulation than *C. catla*. There is concern that people may be exposed to harmful levels of heavy metals from eating these fish over the long term. We need more detailed investigations to fully understand this critical problem.

KEYWORDS: Balloki, *C. catla*, Concentration, *L. rohita*, Heavy Metals, River

Citation: Sagheer, N., S. A. H. ShaH, M. A. Mehmood, and A. Anees. 2023. Determination of heavy metals in vital organs (liver, kidney, and gills) of two fish species from the Head Balloki on River Ravi, Pakistan. International Journal of Forest Sciences. 4: 264-273.

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution is a serious problem that modern civilization must face. Over the past few decades, environmental pollution has been steadily rising due to the expansion of polluting businesses, the rise in the consumption of fossil fuels, and the reckless depletion of natural resources (Sun et al., 2022). Mining, improper waste management, and the burning of fuel are just a few of the human activities that are contributing to the ever-increasing presence of toxic heavy metals in our natural environment (Wedeslassie et al., 2018). Heavy metals are defined as any metallic

elements that have a density that is higher than that of water (Zeitoun and Mehana, 2014). Heavy metals, in particular, are a substantial contributor to environmental contamination for some reasons, including their inherent toxicity and the possibility of bioaccumulation in the food chain (Ilyas et al., 2023; Pujari and Kapoor, 2021). Priority metals include chromium, lead, mercury, arsenic, and cadmium due to their high levels of toxicity. Heavy metals can affect the mitochondria, lysosomes, and other subunits of cells, which can, in turn, affect the metabolic rate, the detoxification process, and the repair of damaged cells (Flora and Agrawal, 2017).

Fish are widely recognized bioindicators of heavy metal levels in water environments and hence form a significant part of most aquatic ecosystems (Authman et al., 2015). Fish are particularly vulnerable because they absorb a disproportionate amount of the aquatic ecosystem (Sadovy de Mitcheson et al., 2013). Fishes' ability to respond to and interact with their surroundings can be impaired by heavy metal poisoning (Hamilton et al., 2016). Fish poisoning from heavy metals is a growing problem across the world (Sonone et al., 2020). Human activities such as leather tanning, metalworking, petroleum refining, textile production, alloy preparation, wood preservatives, etc. all contribute to the accumulation of dangerous levels of chromium in aquatic ecosystems (Ashraf et al., 2019). Chromium's toxicity to aquatic animals is affected by both biotic parameters, such as age, developmental phase, and species, and abiotic ones, such as the water's pH, temperature, and alkalinity (Taslina et al., 2022). Upon first contact with chromium, fish exhibit a variety of abnormal behaviors like erratic swimming, mucous secretion, body color change, lack of appetite, etc. Research has shown that chromium accumulates most strongly in the gills, kidneys, and liver of fish, with a much lower quantity in the fish's muscle tissues (Rajeshkumar and Li, 2018). An excessive amount of chromium in drinking water has been linked to the development of stomach cancers in both humans and animals.

Lead, in the forms of PbS, PbSO₄, and PbCO₃, is one of the most dangerous heavy metals found in nature. Toxic levels of lead in the water are caused by the direct introduction of lead from a variety of sources, including industrial and agricultural areas, street runoff, lead dust, and municipal wastewater (Sankhla et al., 2016). Lead's solubility in water is very context-dependent, necessitating consideration of variables such as pH, salinity, hardness, etc. Lead is more soluble in basic or alkaline water (Jones et al., 2020). Lead at concentrations between 10 and 100 mg/L is fatal to fish. In fish exposed to Pb, the liver is thought to play an important role in metal excretion because of its ability to bind metals to steroids in the bile. Concentration, as well as apocrine, metabolic, and detoxifying mechanisms produced by metal intake, are the primary mechanisms responsible for metal toxicity in fish (Goretti et al., 2016).

Fish exposed to cadmium may exhibit altered behaviors, such as reduced feeding, swimming activity, and predator avoidance. Cadmium can disrupt the endocrine system of fish, leading to hormonal imbalances (Bera et al., 2022). This can affect processes like growth, metabolism, and reproductive functions. Fish can accumulate cadmium from their environment, mainly through the gills during respiration and from the food they consume. Cadmium tends to accumulate in the liver, kidney, and gills of fish (Perera et al., 2016). To mitigate the toxic effects of heavy metals on fish,

it's essential to minimize the release of these heavy metals into aquatic environments through pollution prevention and control measures (Pandey et al., 2014). Monitoring water quality and implementing regulations to limit industrial discharges and other sources of heavy metals can help protect fish and maintain the health of aquatic ecosystems (Naser, 2013).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SAMPLE COLLECTION

A total of 3 randomly selected juvenile freshwater fish, Rohu (*Labeo rohita*) and 3 Thaila (*C. catla*), each 1kg in weight, were taken from the head balloki fish form in Pattoki, Punjab, Pakistan ($31^{\circ}12'11.4''\text{N}$ $73^{\circ}55'33.4''\text{E}$). The selected fish were collected from trap nets and identified using morphological identification keys. The liver and kidneys were taken from the fish, placed in vials, and frozen in preparation for heavy metal analysis.

Figure 1: Map showing location of selected study area from the Head Balloki on River Ravi.

HEAVY METAL ANALYSIS

Samples of liver, gills, and kidneys were temporarily stored in a refrigerator and air-freighted in a cooling box. For heavy metals analysis, the Liver kidneys and gills were dried at 100°C in an oven. Then grind the samples to ground into powder form. Digesting 1.0 g of material in a conical flask with 10 ml of HNO_3 and 15 ml of

H₃PO₄ allowed for the analysis of trace metals. Overnight at room temperature, the sample in the conical flask was allowed to ferment. The samples were then cooked to 120 degrees Celsius on a hot plate with 2 ml of H₂O₂ added the next day. The samples were filtered via filter paper, and distilled water was added to bring the final amount to 50 ml. To preserve the quality of these samples until examination, we chilled them. The atomic inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (PG-900, ICEP- OES) was used to assess metal concentrations in various tissues.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All data is presented as “mean standard deviation”. Graph Pad prism statistical software (Version9.0) was used to compare heavy metals concentration in each organ of each fish. Sidak multiple comparison test was used to compare the concentration of heavy metals in each organ of fish (Gomes et al., 2023).

RESULTS

LIVER

The concentrations of heavy metals in the liver tissues of two fish species, *Labeo rohita* and *Catla catla*, were investigated. For cadmium, *Labeo rohita* showed a concentration of 0.008±0.002 ppm (mg/kg), which was insignificantly higher (P>0.05) than *C. catla* concentration of 0.009±0.002 ppm (mg/kg). Similarly, chromium levels in *L. rohita* (0.024±0.002 ppm) were non-significantly lower (P>0.05) than those in *C. catla* (0.022±0.002 ppm). Notably, lead concentrations in *L. rohita* (0.033±0.002 ppm) were highly significantly lower (P<0.0001) compared to *C. catla* (0.044±0.002 ppm). These findings suggest comparable cadmium and chromium levels between the species, but a significant disparity in lead accumulation, with *C. catla* exhibiting higher concentrations (Table 1 and Figure 2).

Table 1: Concentration of heavy metals in liver, Gills, and Kidney.

Organs	Metals	<i>L.rohita</i>	<i>C.catla</i>	P value
		Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
Liver	Cadmium	0.008±0.002	0.009±0.002	0.8492
	Chromium	0.024±0.002	0.022±0.002	0.8492
	Lead	0.033±0.002	0.044±0.002	<0.0001
Gills	Cadmium	0.012±0.002	0.019±0.002	0.0024
	Chromium	0.014±0.002	0.019±0.003	0.0271
	Lead	0.011±0.002	0.025±0.002	<0.0001
Kidney	Cadmium	0.023±0.002	0.030±0.002	0.0011
	Chromium	0.0434±0.002	0.064±0.003	<0.0001
	Lead	0.16±0.002	0.214±0.002	<0.0001

Figure 2: Comparison of Concentration of heavy metals in liver.

GILLS

Examining the gills of *L. rohita* and *C. catla* provides insights into their heavy metal concentrations. In *L. rohita*, the cadmium level measured 0.012 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), while *C. catla* exhibited a significantly higher concentration at 0.019 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) with a significance level of $P < 0.01$. Chromium concentrations in *L. rohita* (0.014 ± 0.002 ppm) were also detected to be higher, though the difference was the least significant ($P < 0.05$) when compared to *C. catla* (0.019 ± 0.003 ppm). The lead levels in *L. rohita* were recorded at 0.011 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), significantly lower ($P < 0.0001$) than in *C. catla*, where the concentration was 0.025 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg). These findings underline distinct species-specific variations in the accumulation of heavy metals in gill tissues, emphasizing the relevance of such data for ecological and environmental assessments (Figure 3).

Kidney

The analysis of heavy metal concentrations in the kidneys of *Labeo rohita* and *C. catla* reveals distinct patterns. In *L. rohita*, the cadmium concentration was measured at 0.023 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), while *C. catla* exhibited a significantly higher level at 0.030 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) with a significance level of $P < 0.01$. Chromium concentrations in *L. rohita* (0.0434 ± 0.002 ppm) were highly significantly lower ($P < 0.0001$) than those in *C. catla* (0.064 ± 0.003 ppm). The lead levels followed a similar trend, with *L. rohita* registering a concentration of 0.16 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), and *C. catla* showing a highly significantly higher level at 0.214 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) with a significance level of $P < 0.0001$. These findings highlight species-specific

variations in heavy metal accumulation in kidney tissues, emphasizing the importance of considering such disparities in environmental and health assessments (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Statistical comparison of Concentration of heavy metals in Gills

Figure 3: Statistical comparison of heavy metals in kidney.

There are significant differences in the concentrations of all three heavy metals (cadmium, chromium, and lead) between *L. rohita* and *C. catla* in various organs (liver, gills, and kidney). These differences suggest that the two fish species may have distinct patterns of heavy metal accumulation in their tissues. If we have to look, the

overall concentration of lead in the kidney is higher as compared to the gills and liver. The order of lead concentration in fish tissues (kidney > liver > gills) reflects the natural distribution of lead in the fish's body based on their physiological functions. The kidney and liver are the primary sites for detoxification and storage of heavy metals, while the gills, although exposed to waterborne contaminants, do not have the same detoxification and storage capabilities. Cadmium concentrations are highest in the kidney tissues of both *L. rohita* and *C. catla*. This indicates that the kidneys of these fish species accumulate the most cadmium as compared to other organs. Cadmium concentrations are intermediate in the gill tissues of both fish species. While it's lower than in the kidneys, it's still higher compared to the liver. Cadmium concentrations are the lowest in the liver tissues of both *L. rohita* and *C. catla*. This suggests that the liver tends to accumulate the least amount of cadmium among these three organs. Chromium concentrations are higher in the kidney than in the liver and gills (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Concentration of heavy metals in Organs of fish.

DISCUSSION

Due to the propensity to accumulate harmful substances, fish is regarded as an indicator of river health and the potential risks it may pose to human health when consuming contaminated fish. (Abideen et al., 2023; Authman et al., 2015). Studies have indicated that aquatic biota can accumulate toxic metals in their bodies at levels up to a million times higher than the concentrations found in the surrounding water. The elevated concentration of toxic metals in contaminated fish can present a significant risk to human health when consumed (Saelens and Houf, 2022). In the current research, it was observed that the accumulation patterns of metals in the organs of fish differed depending on the type of metal and the species of fish. In general lead exhibits higher concentrations than chromium and cadmium in the

kidney, liver, and gills. These results align with previous studies (El-Moselhy et al., 2014; Ilyas et al., 2023; Squadrone et al., 2013), all of which similarly documented increased metal accumulation in the liver, kidney, and gills of fish. The gills are in direct touch with the surrounding water and can easily absorb hazardous metals from polluted water, whereas the kidneys and liver are involved in metal excretion and detoxification, respectively (Abdel-Khalek et al., 2016).

The current investigation discovered that the average concentration of toxic heavy metals was greater in fish species collected from the Ravi River at Head Balloki. The distribution of Lead, chromium, and cadmium in fish organs collected from River Ravi has been presented in Table 1. In the case of the liver, the concentration of lead in *Labeorohita* was 0.033 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), and in *C. catla* was 0.044 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg), in the case of gills the concentration of lead in *L. rohita* was 0.011 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) and in *C. catla* was 0.025 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) while in case of kidney the concentration of lead in *L. rohita* was 0.16 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg) and in *C. catla* was 0.214 ± 0.002 ppm (mg/kg). The order of concentration of Lead in the tissues of both fishes was kidney > liver > gills. Elevated levels of lead found in the organs of fish suggest that the fish may be at risk of harm. Lead toxicity can lead to a range of adverse effects in fish, including impaired growth, reproductive problems, altered behavior, and damage to internal organs. The severity of these effects depends on the concentration of lead, the duration of exposure, and the species of fish. If humans consume fish contaminated with elevated levels of lead, there is a risk of lead exposure to humans. Lead exposure can affect the nervous system, kidney function, and other organs.

In this study lead accumulation was shown to be much higher than that of other heavy metals. *C. catla* and *L. rohita* were found to have the lowest cadmium levels among all the fish tested. Cadmium deposits were first found in the kidneys of both of the fish, then in the gills, and ultimately in the livers of both of the fish. In addition to being a very lethal metal, cadmium serves no important biological purpose in humans. The order of concentration of cadmium in the tissue of *L. rohita* and *C. catla* was kidney > gills > liver. The order of concentration of chromium in the tissue of both Rohu and Thaila was kidney > liver > gills and the order of concentration of Lead in the tissues of both fishes was kidney > liver > gills. The finding that lead exhibits the highest overall concentration among the tested heavy metals in both fish species highlights the particular concern associated with lead contamination in these freshwater ecosystems. Lead toxicity can have wide-ranging effects on fish populations and can bioaccumulate through the food chain, ultimately impacting human health when these fish are consumed.

CONCLUSION

According to the findings of the current study kidneys, liver, and gills of fish were shown to be the organs that had the most potential for bio-accumulation. According to the findings, the sequence of the concentration of heavy metals was as follows: lead > chromium > cadmium. The kidney was found to have the largest concentration of heavy metals, followed by the liver, and then the gills. In addition to this, it was discovered that *L. rohita* has a greater buildup of heavy metals than *C. catla* does. It is possible that in the future there may be an increase in the danger of metallic

toxicity. This will depend on the amount of wastewater from adjacent human activities, both industrial and municipal, that flows into the river Ravi.

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